

Thermosensitivity of rice seeds grown by farmers

L. P. Kauraw and N. K. Chakrabarti, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack-753 006, India

Treating rice seeds with hot water is recommended to control externally and internally borne pathogens like fungi, bacteria, and nematodes. Treatment use is limited because of the differential sensitivity of seeds to hot water. It is necessary to determine the thermosensitivity of seed of different rice varieties before subjecting them to hot water treatment. This study was made to ascertain rice sensitivity to hot water treatment at recommended temperatures (52 or 54°C).

Seeds of 13 improved semidwarf rice varieties — IR8 (Peta/DgWg), Vani (IR8/CR1014), Jagannath (TI41 mutant), Kalinga-1 (Dungharsali/IR8), Ratna (TKM6/IR8), Pankaj (Tonkai Raton/Peta), Parijat (TKM6/TN1), Indira (Tainan 3 mutant), CR 158-5008-52-212, CR10-4181-10, CR9242, local Athgadi, BJ 1 — and the improved tall variety TI41 were collected from farmers in the CRRI Operational Research Project Area at Kandarpur in Cuttack, Orissa.

Twenty-five grams seed of each variety were placed in separate cloth bags, soaked in room temperature water for 8 hours, and then separately treated in a Kilburn hot water bath at 52 or 54°C for 10, 20, and 30 minutes. They were then dipped in water at room temperature. Untreated controls were main-

Percentage of seed germination of rice varieties treated with hot water at 52 and 54°C for 10, 20, and 30 minutes in Cuttack, India.

Variety	Temperature (°C)	Germination (%)			
		Control	10 min	20 min	30 min
IR8	52	59.00	46.50	34.50	21.75
	54	59.25	40.50	26.25	18.00
Vani	52	29.00	29.75	25.50	26.75
	54	41.00	40.00	35.00	25.50
Jagannath	52	51.25	40.00	23.60	14.00
	54	54.00	35.00	21.50	8.50
CR9242	52	45.25	35.00	24.25	20.50
	54	48.00	40.00	28.75	23.25
Kalinga-1	52	58.50	60.00	45.75	35.00
	54	61.75	59.00	44.50	32.25
CR158-5008-52-212	52	53.75	38.75	29.75	29.25
	54	49.50	38.50	29.00	24.00
TI41	52	57.50	60.00	40.00	41.50
	54	60.50	58.25	38.50	30.75
Ratna	52	74.50	71.00	68.50	68.75
	54	77.25	77.50	69.00	42.25
Athgadi	52	69.25	66.25	58.00	39.00
	54	70.00	67.00	53.00	29.75
Pankaj	52	72.50	69.25	55.00	57.75
	54	71.75	66.00	48.50	26.50
BJ 1	52	50.00	52.50	48.00	45.00
	54	55.75	54.00	46.50	41.00
CR10-4181-10	52	46.00	44.00	47.00	44.75
	54	48.15	44.50	32.25	27.00
Indira	52	79.00	74.00	76.25	77.25
	54	81.50	74.00	45.75	35.00
Parijat	52	66.75	54.00	42.25	31.00
	54	72.50	58.25	44.00	33.50

tained for each variety and treatment. Germination of 400 seeds was tested by the blotter method.

Germination was reduced for all varieties when seeds were placed in 54°C water for 30 minutes. Seeds of Ratna, Indira, BJ 1, CR10-4181-10, and Vani were insensitive to treatment at 52°C for 30 minutes. Athgadi, Kalinga-1, TI41,

and Pankaj were insensitive to 52 and 54°C temperatures when exposed for 10 minutes only, but germination was reduced when the seeds were exposed for 20 or 30 minutes. Jagannath, IR8, CR9242, CR158-5008-52-212, and Parijat were very sensitive to hot water. Germination declined as exposure time and temperature increased (see table).

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Yield, plant characteristics, and quality of some rice varieties in the Amazon Valley

G. C. Shukla, rice agronomist, Instituto de Pesquisas (IRI), Caixa Postal 258, 66000 Belém, Pará, Brazil

Five to ten million hectares in the lower Amazon basin of Brazil are swampy for most of the year. Little land is reclaimed

for planting. At São Raimundo, land was diked and a fully mechanized project established. Seeding and fertilizer and pesticide application are done aerially. Crops are harvested by combines. Electric pumps facilitate irrigation and drainage.

Soils are acidic and have high exchangeable iron and aluminum content. In a preliminary seed multiplication

trial superior varieties were selected. Using these varieties, a replicated yield trial was conducted in 1981 to isolate high yielding varieties with good grain quality. Rough rice yields at 14% moisture and plant ancillary characteristics are in Table 1. Milling yields and grain quality are in Table 2.

Varieties had significant yield differences. Variety J-229 is the present com-

Table 1. Yield and plant ancillary characteristics from varietal yield trial experiments, São Raimundo, Brazil, 1981.^a

Entry	Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Effective tillers/plant	Lodging (%)	Days to flowering	Days to maturity
J-32	IR22	6.78	108	19	1	103	138
J-40	IR24	7.91	98	20	1	93	126
J-179	IR36	7.63	86	27	3	85	116
J-229	P738-97-3-1	7.56	100	20	1	103	136
J-233	Juma 58	6.71	118	18	1	111	145
J-266	IR11248-52-2-3-3	6.59	113	27	7	95	126
J-301	IET6503	6.16	104	25	3	85	118
J-305	IAC899-55-6-4-6	7.84	116	21	1	94	128
J-310	P1291	9.00	123	18	1	104	136
J-311 (Phil.)	BR51-46-1-C-1	7.25	118	20	5	98	130
J-311 (S.P.)	BR51-46-1-C-1	7.50	122	18	1	101	134
J-314	IR665-23-3-1	7.61	106	19	1	98	131
J-319	IET5518 (CR35-2740)	6.79	103	21	1	84	115
J-323	IR9129-7-1	6.38	86	23	1	77	110
J-324	IR9129-102-2	6.55	96	24	1	82	114
J-325	IR9168-13-1	8.00	107	23	1	85	116
J-327	UPR70	5.08	90	22	1	82	113
LSD (0.05)		0.90					
CV (%)		8.90					

^aGermplasm for J-311 (Phil.) was received from the Philippines and J-311 (S.P.) from the Instituto Agrônomico de Campinas, Brazil.

mercial variety. It was compared with J-310, J-311 (S.P.), J-311 (Phil.), J-314, J-325, J-40, J-179, and J-305. Variety J-310 yielded best but had high opacity and broken grain percentage. J-311 (S.P.), which was resistant to leaf blast, needs further testing in large plots. Most J-311 (Phil.) plants lodged. J-314, J-179, and J-324 had a low percentage of whole grains and a high percentage of opacity. J-40 was susceptible to leaf blast and neck blast. J-305 had medium (5.87 mm) grain length. Variety J-266, which gave good results in 1980, yielded low and lodged severely. It had medium grain length. *h*

Table 2. Grain quality and milling yields of different varieties, São Raimundo, Brazil, 1981.

Entry	Milling yield (%)	Whole grains (%)	Opacity (%)	Grain length (mm)	Grain width (mm)	L/W ^a ratio
J-32	71.28	61.92	11	6.82	2.44	2.80
J-40	69.44	49.44	13	6.76	2.04	3.31
J-179	72.56	35.44	28	6.43	1.87	3.44
J-229	67.52	46.50	14	6.55	2.12	3.09
J-233	67.20	44.16	32	6.72	2.25	2.99
J-266	71.52	52.90	14	5.88	2.11	2.79
J-301	70.08	46.32	13	6.49	1.77	3.66
J-305	69.92	54.32	12	5.87	2.00	2.94
J-310	72.72	53.04	33	7.17	2.11	3.40
J-311 (Phil.)	72.88	60.80	20	6.60	2.19	3.01
J-311 (S.P.)	70.80	53.60	23	6.50	2.28	2.85
J-314	69.68	39.10	35	7.16	2.00	3.58
J-319	72.56	57.84	17	7.14	2.08	3.43
J-323	72.24	58.64	12	6.40	2.02	3.39
J-324	70.72	44.48	18	6.59	2.05	3.21
J-325	71.28	35.20	38	7.32	2.13	3.44
J-327	66.16	55.84	33	6.87	2.01	3.42

^aLength-width.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Rice panicle type for high grain yields in low temperature areas

B. S. Vergara, J. H. Lee, G. Pateña, J. D. Yea, and R. M. Visperas, IRR

High rice yields result from large numbers of spikelets per unit area.

Number of spikelets depends on panicles per unit area and spikelets per panicle.

In modern varieties planted in the tropics, increased yield is generally pro-

Table 1. 1981 IRCTN entries by grain yield, panicle number per hill, and spikelets per panicle. Chuncheon, Korea, 1981.

Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelets/panicle	Entries (no.) with given panicles/hill				
		4-6	7-9	10-12	13-15	16-18
>6	<130	0	0	10	8	2
	>130	1	5	10	1	0
<6	<130	1	27	32	9	0
	>130	4	29	21	4	0

duced by increasing panicle number (panicle number type). In traditional indica varieties with limited panicle

number at flowering, yield is multiplied by increasing panicle weight or spikelets per panicle (panicle weight type).